

CAN catalyzed synthesis of 1*H*-indazolotriones

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Abstract : We have developed a potential method for the synthesis of biologically active¹ 2,2'-dimethyl-13-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-indazolo[2,1-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11(13*H*)-trione and its derivatives via an one-pot, four-component synthesis of phthalic anhydride, hydrazine, aromatic aldehydes and dimedone in the presence of ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) at room temperature. The reaction was completed within 30 min yielding 70–90% of the corresponding product. The reaction was extended to different aldehydes and anhydrides leading to good yields in all the cases.

Keywords : Phthalhydrazide, CAN, indazolo triones.

Introduction

Multicomponent reactions may be considered as greener protocols as they lead to the reduction of by-products. Avoiding the usage of toxic organic solvents, strongly acidic conditions and large amount of catalysts are the added advantages in addition to lower energy costs, simple workup procedures and improved yield and selectivity of products. So, the multicomponent reaction may be used as a powerful and successful method for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds. According to the principle of green chemistry, synthetic methods should cause a little or no toxicity to human health and the environment².

Nitrogen heterocycles with a phthalazine moiety are considered as significant compounds because they show biological and pharmacological activities such as anticonvulsant, cardiogenic and vasorelaxant, and also shows unique electrical and optical properties³. Multicomponent reactions of cyclic diketone, an aldehyde, nitrogen containing nucleophilic compounds have recently attracted interest as they can be used to produce a range of building blocks³. Heterocyclic fused indazolo derivatives having two nitrogen atoms in a bridgehead position can be obtained by the condensation of an anhydride, hydrazine, aromatic aldehydes and dimedone in the presence of catalysts like $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ⁴, heteropoly acid⁵ etc.

Most of the processes reported for the synthesis of the above said compounds suffered from limitations such as harsh reaction conditions, tedious work-up procedures,

relatively long reaction times, higher temperatures and expensive reagents. Therefore, the search continues for a better catalyst for the synthesis of heterocycles containing phthalazine moiety in terms of operational simplicity, economic and environment friendly.

Ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN), being a water compatible Lewis acid has been employed for a variety of synthetic transformations due to its low-cost, easy availability, eco-friendly non-toxic nature and feasibility of easier work-up procedures. In this regard we have planned to use the CAN as the catalyst for the synthesis of indazolotrione derivatives.

Results and discussion

The development of newer synthetic methodologies for the construction of 1*H*-indazolotrione derivatives will be a useful and interesting challenge. We have developed a synthetic method for the indazolo trione derivatives via a novel, one-pot four-component condensation involving a sequential addition of the reactants via phthalic anhydride, hydrazine, aromatic aldehydes, and dimedone in ethanolic medium using CAN as a catalyst (Scheme 1). The enhanced reactivity of ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) has led to its emergence as a promising Lewis acid catalyst⁶.

Mol% of CAN has been optimized by using 5, 10, 20 mol% and good yields were obtained with 20 mol% in shorter duration. There was no more significant effect on the product yield or reaction time beyond 20 mol% of the

Scheme 1. Reaction scheme for the formation of indazolo triones.

catalyst. Similarly, we found that ethanol as a suitable solvent after screening various other solvents such as methanol, acetonitrile and acetone.

The generality of this reaction was examined by using both electron withdrawing and electron donating substituents on the aldehydes under the same reaction conditions, and observed that the yields were good irrespective of the substituents present. Significant improvements of this method are the scope of the transformation, simplicity, and green aspects by avoiding expensive or corrosive catalysts.

A possible mechanism for the formation of the products is shown in Scheme 2. Coordination of Ce^{IV} ion to one of the carbonyl carbons of phthalic anhydride en-

Ce^{IV} ion catalyzed formation of heterodyne by standard Knoevenagel condensation of dimecane and aldehyde. Subsequent Michael-type addition of the phthalhydrazide followed by cyclization afforded the corresponding product.

Experimental

The melting points of all compounds were determined with an electrothermal apparatus using capillary tube and are uncorrected. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance spectrophotometer at 400/100 MHz respectively using TMS as reference.

To the mixture of 1 mmol of phthalic anhydride, 20 mol% of CAN in 10 ml of ethanol and 1 mmol of hydrazine were added. Immediately a white precipitate was formed while stirring at room temperature. To this mixture 1 mmol of aromatic aldehyde was added followed by 1 mmol of dimecane and stirred at room temperature for about 1 h as indicated in Table 1. A yellow precipitate, indazolo trione derivative formed has been separated by simple filtration, washed with distilled water and then dried. The product was characterized by the NMR studies.

3,4-Dihydro-3,3'-dimethyl-13-phenyl-2H-indazolo[2,1-b]phthalazine-1,6,11-(13H)-trione (5a): Yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.20 (6H, s), 2.34 (2H,

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism for the formation of indazolo triones.

hances the nucleophilic addition of hydrazine to phthalic anhydride followed by dehydration leading to the formation of phthalhydrazide. The second step involves the

s), 3.27 (1H, dd), 3.44 (1H, d), 6.47 (1H, s), 7.31–8.36 (9H, m) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 28.4, 28.6, 34.6, 38.1, 50.8, 64.8, 118.7, 127.2, 127.6,

Table 1. CAN catalyzed four component synthesis of 2*H*-indazolo[2,1-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11-(13*H*)-trione derivatives in ethanol at room temperature

Sr. no.	Aldehyde (X)	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)	Compound name	m.p. (°C)
1.	H	1.5	79	5a	207–209
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl	1.0	85	5b	262–264
3.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.0	84	5c	222–224
4.	<i>p</i> -F	1.5	82	5d	221–223
5.	<i>p</i> -OMe	1.0	81	5e	220–222

127.9, 128.6, 128.9, 129.3, 133.7, 134.6, 136.3, 150.8, 154.4, 156.2, 192.3 ppm.

*13-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3,3'-dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-indazolo[1,2-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11-(13H)-trione (5b)* : Yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.21 (6H, s), 2.34 (2H, s), 3.21–3.44 (2H, m), 6.42 (1H, s), 7.29–8.35 (8H, m) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 28.4, 28.7, 34.7, 38.0, 50.9, 64.3, 118.6, 127.0, 127.1, 127.7, 128.6, 128.9, 129.1, 133.7, 134.4, 136.3, 150.8, 154.2, 156.1, 192.4 ppm.

*3,3-Dimethyl-13-(4-nitrophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-indazolo[1,2-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11-(13H)-trione (5c)* : Yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.26 (6H, s), 2.34 (2H, s), 3.29–3.54 (2H, m), 6.47 (1H, s), 7.32–8.46 (8H, m) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 28.4, 28.7, 34.7, 38.0, 50.9, 64.3, 118.6, 127.0, 127.1, 127.7, 128.6, 128.9, 129.1, 133.7, 134.4, 136.3, 150.8, 154.2, 156.1, 192.4 ppm.

*3,3-Dimethyl-13-(4-fluorophenyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-indazolo[1,2-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11-(13H)-trione (5d)* : Yellow solid. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 1.24 (6H, s), 2.32 (2H, s), 3.26–3.50 (2H, m), 6.47 (1H, s), 7.32–8.46 (8H, m) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 28.1, 28.4, 34.5, 38.1, 50.7, 64.2, 118.4, 127.2, 127.4,

127.8, 128.4, 128.9, 129.1, 133.7, 134.4, 136.3, 150.8, 153.2, 156.6, 192.9 ppm.

Conclusion

In summary, an efficient one-pot synthesis of 2*H*-indazolo[2,1-*b*]phthalazine-1,6,11(13*H*)-trione derivatives has been described under room temperature conditions using inexpensive starting materials. Upto our knowledge, synthesis of indazolo trione using CAN as a catalyst in this method may be a good example for the simple organic transformations of some small molecules to a bigger molecules having biological moiety.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor M. Periasamy and UGC Networking Resource Centre, University of Hyderabad, India for providing the spectral facilities. KR thanks Jawaharlal Nehru Memorial Fund for Doctoral Studies for the financial support.

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